

Integrated quasi-steady wind farm flow control / D1.2

WP1, T1.2

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the contributions of T1.2 on *integrated quasi-steady wind farm flow control* as part of the SUDOCO project's *Control Room of the Future*. A major challenge in wind farm operations is mitigating the negative impact of wind turbine wakes on power output and structural loads. This report investigates three primary wind farm flow control strategies: static induction control, wake steering, and wake mixing techniques. While static induction control and wake steering have been widely studied, wake mixing techniques, including periodic dynamic induction control, the helix method, and dynamic yaw control, require further research before integration into existing modelling tools.

The objectives of this report focus on the development and implementation of wake control techniques. The report introduces a data-driven framework, which employs Gaussian processes to model the performance of wake-mixing techniques and find the optimal controller setting. Additionally, a quasi-steady wake model has been developed and integrated into the PyWake engineering wake model to evaluate wake mixing techniques. A wind farm control optimisation tool is also introduced to estimate optimal control settings using parameterised solution spaces. Furthermore, a benchmark of wind farm flow control techniques is conducted using high-fidelity simulations of a reference wind farm. To complement these findings, wind tunnel experiments were performed to compare static and dynamic yaw control on scaled wind turbine models.

The results indicate that wake mixing techniques, particularly the helix method and dynamic yaw control, can achieve significant power gains in scenarios with full turbine wake overlap. In partial wake overlap scenarios, wake steering shows superior performance. Comparisons between wake steering and wake mixing showed that the effectiveness of each method depends on factors such as wind direction, turbine alignment, and atmospheric boundary layer height.

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1 Introduction

The overall aim of the SUDOCO project (“SUstainable resilient Data-enabled Off-shore wind farm and control CO-design”) is to develop the **Control Room of the Future**. This control room will enable real-time optimization of wind farm performance through advanced flow control strategies and potential synergies with energy storage solutions such as batteries or hydrogen systems. The control room optimises power production and turbine structural health over their lifetimes, balancing financial and ecological performance.

To achieve this, SUDOCO integrates state-of-the-art numerical tools for modelling wind farm wake aerodynamics and the aero-servo-elastic responses of turbines. These tools are fully coupled to capture the complex interactions within the wind farm and to guide operations through an overarching wind farm controller. The results of this work will contribute to the integration efforts within WP2 and WP3, supporting the development of a comprehensive control framework for wind farms. This research also lays the groundwork for WP4, which aims to integrate these advancements into the control room of the future, enhancing wind farm operation and management.

1.1 Wind farm flow control

Wind turbine wakes can have a large negative impact on the overall power output of a wind farm, as well as on the structural loads of individual turbines. The extent of the wake effect depends on wind farm topology, wind direction, and the ambient wake recovery. However, it is possible to partially mitigate wake effects through wind farm flow control. Wind farm control methods are generally divided into three branches: *Static induction control*, *wake steering*, and *dynamic induction control* or *wake mixing* methods (Meyers et al., 2022).

Static induction control purposefully decreases the power output of upstream turbines to enhance the performance of turbines operating in a wake (Corten and Schaak, 2003). This can be done by either offsetting the blade pitch angles, or altering the generator torque controller to change the rotor speed setpoint. Although static induction control can achieve reductions in structural loads, simulation studies and field experiments have not been able to demonstrate significant gains in power (Hoek et al., 2019).

Wake steering involves intentionally misaligning upstream turbines with the wind direction to deflect their wakes away from the downstream turbines. While the mis-

alignment of the upstream turbines decreases their power capture, the overall power of a farm is enhanced. Many studies have been done on wake steering to show its capabilities in both high-fidelity simulation environments (Gebraad et al., 2016) and in field experiments (Fleming et al., 2017).

Wake mixing techniques have received increasing attention in the scientific field over the last few years. Control methods that fall under this category have in common that they rely on the dynamic adjustment of one of the wind turbine's control set-points, such as the pitch or yaw angles. By continually changing the control inputs, we hope to excite the wake and enhance the natural wake recovery mechanism. Examples of wake mixing methods are *periodic dynamic induction control* (Munters and Meyers, 2018b), the *helix method* (Frederik et al., 2020a) and the *dynamic yaw approach* first studied by Munters and Meyers (2018a). With periodic dynamic induction control, the collective blade pitch angle is varied, generally following a sinusoidal pattern, to change the magnitude of the thrust force applied to the incoming flow over time. The helix method employs individual pitch control to periodically vary the direction of the thrust force, resulting in a helically shaped wake. Dynamic yaw control consists of a periodical variation of the yaw angle, which translates into an increased meandering motion of the wake and thus an increase in wake mixing.

1.2 Deliverable outline

The previous section briefly introduced different wind farm flow control options. While some of these methods have already been studied extensively, more recent methods, such as the wake mixing techniques, require additional steps before they can be integrated in existing wake modelling tools. This report presents the objectives and methodologies proposed in WP1 Task 1.2, which focuses on investigating and developing wake control techniques for wind farms. More specifically, we will only focus on the quasi-steady implementation of wind farm control methods, meaning their implementation in ambient conditions with a fixed mean wind speed and wind direction, or the use of steady-state wake models. The deliverable will cover the following topics:

- The development of a data-driven framework employing Gaussian processes and Bayesian optimisation for tuning wake mixing controllers.
- A quasi-steady wake model capturing the effect of wake mixing techniques on the wake that will be integrated in the existing engineering wake model PyWake.
- A brief demonstration of a wind farm control optimisation tool that uses a parameterised solution space to find the optimal control settings.

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- A benchmark of the previously covered wind farm flow control techniques using high-fidelity simulations on a reference wind farm.
- A wind tunnel experiment comparing static and dynamic yaw control on scaled wind turbine models.

To achieve these objectives, a series of high-fidelity simulations is conducted based on reference scenarios. The methods to obtain these results are discussed in Chapter 2. Next, the data-driven approach for tuning the wake mixing controllers is presented in Chapter 3. This framework allows us to minimise the number of high-fidelity simulations while ensuring the identification of optimal controller settings. Chapter 4 introduces a quasi-steady wake surrogate model that is developed to evaluate wake mixing strategies. Such a model enables rapid assessment of control strategies by capturing the steady-state nature of the wake without requiring time-intensive transient simulations, making them particularly useful for real-time applications and optimization workflows. An example of such an optimisation is provided in Chapter 5, which presents a brief look into an optimisation framework for steady-state wake models. A case study is performed to demonstrate the framework by optimising the control inputs for wake steering on the reference wind farm. In Chapter 6, a broad set of large eddy simulations is carried out at both the subcluster and wind farm level, to benchmark the different control strategies in terms of the power improvement they achieve. Next, the results from a wind tunnel campaign are presented in Chapter 7, where we compared wake steering to dynamic yaw control, and also investigated the combination of both methods. The deliverable is finalised in Chapter 8 with the conclusions.

2 Methods

This chapter introduces some of the tools used to generate the results for this deliverable. In Section 2.1, the reference wind farms that will be simulated with large eddy simulations (LES) and engineering wake models will be briefly discussed. Next, Section 2.2 gives an overview of the simulation codes that were used by the different partners.

2.1 Reference wind farms

For the simulations that will be performed in this deliverable, we will consider the reference wind farms as defined in D1.1. These reference wind farms include the CL-Windcon reference layout of 9 turbines in a rectangular grid (CL-Windcon, 2017), and the Hollandse Kust Noord (HKN) wind farm located in the North Sea near the Dutch coast. The latter consists of 69 11-MW wind turbines with a rotor diameter of 200m. A visualisation of the layout of the wind farm is provided in Figure 2.1. Within the SUDOCO project, we consider a scaled-up version of this layout to represent future wind farms with larger turbines. To this effect, we used the IEA-22MW reference turbine (Zahle et al., 2024) in all of our simulations. The turbine has a hub height of 170m and a rotor diameter of $D = 284\text{m}$. The nominal power output is 22MW and the rated wind speed is 11 m/s.

Figure 2.1: Layout of the Hollandse Kust Noord wind farm. The turbines marked in red are part of the South-West corner of the wind farm that will be studied in his deliverable.

After replacing the wind turbines in the HKN layout, we obtain a wind farm that covers an area of approximately $25 \times 25 \text{ km}^2$. Simulating such a large domain using large-eddy simulations is computationally infeasible when comparing multiple control strategies. Therefore, we decided to limit the simulations to the South Western corner of the HKN wind farm consisting of 10 wind turbines with interesting wake interaction and corresponding to the free-wind sector with predominant wind direction. The layout is visualised in Figure 2.2, and shows three arrays with close turbine spacing that will see significant wake interaction depending on the wind direction.

Figure 2.2: Layout of the HKN wind farm SW corner scaled with the diameter (D) of the IEA-22MW turbine. The rectangular boxes show the 2 (left) and 3-turbine (right) arrays that have also been simulated within this deliverable.

This deliverable contains multiple case studies, where we considered different reference wind farms, control methods, or simulators. An overview of all the simulation cases is shown in Tab. 2.1. For the controller tuning framework presented in Chapter 3, it is sufficient to consider only two turbines. For this purpose, we chose the two-turbine array with $5D$ spacing as shown in one of the rectangular boxes in Figure 2.2. Furthermore, when evaluating different control strategies in Chapter 6 that required the implementation of an Actuator Line Model (ALM), we only simulated the two and three-turbine arrays indicated in the figure. For the benchmark simulations on wake steering that implemented the Actuator Disk Method (ADM), the entire HKN SW corner was simulated. The three-turbine array that we simulated is very similar to the rectangular layout of the CL-Windcon reference wind farm, which has three rows separated by $5D$ and three columns separated by $7D$ (CL-Windcon, 2017). Therefore, we decided not to run any additional simulations of the CL-Windcon farm as the results would presumably be very similar.

Table 2.1: Overview of all the wind farm simulation cases that are considered in this report.

Simulation case	Reference wind farm	Simulator	Chapter
Wake mixing controller tuning	two-turbine array	AMR-Wind	3
Quasi-steady helix wake model	HKN SW (10 turbines)	PyWake	4
WFFC optimisation framework	HKN SW (10 turbines)	PyWake	5
Static and dynamic yaw control	two-turbine array	SOWFA	6
WFFC benchmark study	two/three-turbine array	AMR-Wind	6
Wake steering for HKN SW	HKN SW (10 turbines)	EllipSys3D	6

2.2 Wind farm simulation tools

Within this deliverable, various software tools were used for simulations. This chapter provides a detailed explanation of these software tools and the simulation setup. Different partners in the project utilised their own frameworks, as each developed their own simulation environment. Nevertheless, all the tools are robust and incorporate up-to-date levels of detail.

2.2.1 Ellipsys3D/Dynamiks

The DTU flow solver EllipSys3D (Michelsen, 1994; Michelsen, 1992; Sørensen, 1995) is a three-dimensional multi-block incompressible Navier-Stokes solver developed in-house, which uses a finite volume method to solve the governing equations expressed in general curvilinear coordinates in a collocated grid. A second-order accurate three-level implicit method is used for time advancement, with sub-iterations within each time step. A SIMPLEC approach is used to solve the pressure correction equation (Shen et al., 2003; Kobayashi and Pereira, 1991) with Rhie/Chow interpolation to avoid odd/even decoupling. A fourth-order central differencing scheme, including a fourth-order dissipation term to reduce numerical instabilities, is used to discretise convective terms (Wit and Rhee, 2013). When simulating non-neutral atmospheric boundary layers including temperature effects, the potential temperature transport equation is also solved, and Monin-Obukhov similarity theory (Monin and Obukhov, 1954) is used to calculate the instantaneous surface shear stress at the lowest grid cell. Turbulence modelling is achieved using Large Eddy Simulations (LES). LES explicitly resolves all turbulent scales larger than a filter size (which is generally equivalent to the grid size) and models all smaller scales, hence explicitly capturing the large-scale energy-transporting turbulent motions. The sub-grid scale model used here is the Anisotropic Minimum-Dissipation (AMD) model (Abkar et al., 2016).

For the simulations using EllipSys3D, precursor simulations are used to generate two conventionally neutral boundary layer (CNBL) inflows with different boundary layer heights, which are used as inflow to a successor domain containing the wind

farm. The precursor simulation technique and the resulting inflows are the same as those used for the reference wind farm simulations in SUDOCO deliverable 1.1 (hence, for further details of the numerical setup of the precursor simulations, see the D1.1 report). Figure 2.3, reproduced from D1.1, displays the main inflow characteristics.

Figure 2.3: Time- and horizontally-averaged profiles of the CNBL precursors with initial inversion height of 150m and 500m: A) Velocity Magnitude U_{mag} ; B) Turbulence Intensity, $TI = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}k}/U_{mag}$. The rotor area is shown in grey for comparison. Reproduced from D1.1.

Wind turbines are modelled in Ellipsys3D using an actuator disc (AD) model (Mikkelsen, 2004), which is coupled to the aero-servo-elastic solver HAWC2 (Larsen and Hansen, 2007) through the Dynamiks framework¹. The AD represents the impact of the wind turbine on the flow by applying body forces inside the computational domain, over a disc representing the rotor area. The forces applied to represent the wind turbine are calculated through the Dynamiks coupling as follows: EllipSys3D extracts the flow velocities at the blade locations and sends them to Dynamiks, which passes them to HAWC2. HAWC2 uses the velocities to calculate the blade forces and deflections based on tabulated 2D-aerofoil data. These forces are returned to Dynamiks and used to set the actuator forces and locations within EllipSys3D, using a Gaussian smearing to prevent numerical instabilities. This means that both the influence of non-uniform loading, and the effect of blade deflection on the flow is modelled (Hodgson et al., 2021). HAWC2 is a multi-body finite-element solver which uses Timoshenko beam theory, and therefore can also capture the effect of torsional deflection, which is important for very large turbines such as the IEA22MW. A turbine controller is also included, which allows the rotational speed and blade pitch of the turbine to change in response to the dynamic inflow variations.

¹<https://dynamiks.pages.windenergy.dtu.dk/dynamiks/>

2.2.2 AMR-Wind

The Adaptive Mesh Refinement for Wind (AMR-WIND) (Exawind, 2023) simulation tool was developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) and Sandia National Laboratories. It is part of the ExaWind modeling and simulation environment (Sharma et al., 2024), built on top of the AmRex library (Zhang et al., 2019). AMR-Wind solves the three-dimensional incompressible Navier–Stokes equations in a spatially filtered resolved-scale formulation and employs a subgrid-scale model for smaller eddy dynamics. Furthermore, the code uses the Boussinesq approximation to account for the impact of density gradients on buoyancy.

In all atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) simulations, turbulence was modeled, using the one equation subgrid-scale turbulence model (Moeng, 1984), which introduces a transport equation for subgrid-scale turbulent kinetic energy by dynamically computing the eddy viscosity. This makes it suitable for high Reynolds number flows commonly found in the ABL. The bottom boundary of the simulation domain used a wall shear stress model using Monin-Obukhov similarity theory. A slip wall definition for the velocity along with a fixed potential temperature gradient were set for the top part of the domain.

Precursor simulations of a conventionally neutral boundary layer with similar conditions to the North Sea were run to generate the turbulent inflow for the wind farm simulations. An example of a precursor simulation for an average hub height wind speed of $U_\infty = 10\text{m/s}$ is given in Figure 2.4, showing the average wind speed U , turbulence intensity I and wind veer ϕ profiles over domain height.

Figure 2.4: Average profiles of wind speed (U), turbulence intensity (I) and wind veer (ϕ) for one the precursor simulations in AMR-Wind. The dash-dotted line indicates the turbine hub-height, while the shaded areas indicate the height spanned by the wind turbine rotor.

In the case of single turbine simulations that were employed in Chapter 4, turbulence was modelled using the $k - \Omega$ SST-IDDES model (Gritskevich et al., 2011), which employs a Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) solver for attached flow regions while switching to a LES solver for detached flow regions. The small-scale turbulence in the detached region was modelled, using the Smagorinsky subgrid-

scale model. This method ensures high computational efficiency, while still being able to accurately model the wake behind the turbine.

Wind farm simulations used the coupling between AMR-Wind and the aeroelastic simulator OpenFAST (Jonkman, 2013) to model the wind turbine response. The aerodynamic forces of the turbine are modelled using OpenFAST, which are subsequently applied to the incoming flow using the actuator line method (ALM). The ALM model consists of 59 actuator points, matching the number of available airfoil files. The selected Gaussian kernel width ε for distributing the forces at the actuator points was based on a prior conducted thrust convergence study. An overview of all the simulation settings is provided in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2: Settings for the simulations performed with AMR-Wind.

Domain size	$16D \times 16D \times 4.6D$
Cell size (base mesh)	$10\text{ m} \times 10\text{ m} \times 10\text{ m}$
Cell size (refined mesh)	$5\text{ m} \times 5\text{ m} \times 5\text{ m}$
Blade epsilon	$2\Delta x = 10\text{ m}$
Rotor approximation	Actuator Line Method
ABL stability	Neutral
Inversion height z_i	700 m
Inflow wind speed U_∞	8, 10 m/s
Inflow wind direction ϕ	240° (south-west)
Surface roughness z_0	0.001 (TI=4%)
Simulation length (precursor)	36,000 s
Simulation length (successor)	4,200 s
Time step	0.05 s

Control signals for the turbine were implemented using the reference open-source controller (ROSCO) toolbox for wind turbine applications (Abbas et al., 2022). In simulations of the Helix control strategy, slowly varying tilt and yaw signals are imposed on the turbine. These signals are designed in a non-rotating reference frame and then translated to the rotating reference frame by using the Multi-Blade Coordinate transformation (Bir, 2008).

2.2.3 SOWFA

The Simulator fOr Wind Farm Applications (Churchfield and Lee, 2012) is a computational fluid dynamics (CFD) tool developed by NREL. It is based on OpenFOAM (Weller et al., 1998) and is widely used to simulate wind turbine wakes and wind farms. Similar to AMR-Wind, OpenFOAM's LES applies a spatially filtered formulation to resolve large-scale turbulence structures while modeling the effects of smaller eddies using subgrid-scale models. SOWFA couples OpenFOAM and OpenFAST (Jonkman, 2013) to simulate wind farm aerodynamics and turbine dynamics. The Actuator Line Method (Sørensen and Shen, 2002) was used to represent wind turbine blades and to model the impact of time-dependent variations in aerodynamic

forces. The atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) was modeled using TurbSim (Kelley and Jonkman, 2007), a stochastic wind field generator tool developed by NREL. TurbSim generates realistic ABL wind fields by using spectral turbulence models, which account for spatial and temporal correlations of wind turbulence. It combines a logarithmic wind profile, statistical turbulence characteristics, and numerical methods to create time-varying wind velocities at multiple heights, which are then used in wind turbine simulations.

Table 2.3: Settings for the simulations performed with SOWFA.

Domain size	$21D \times 5D \times 5D$
Turbine location	$6D$ from inlet
Cell size (coarse)	$\Delta x \approx 0.11D$
Cell size (finest)	$0.007D$
Rotor approximation	Actuator Line Method
Inflow wind speed	8.0 m/s
Simulation length	500 s
Time step length	0.02 s

2.2.4 PyWake

PyWake (Pedersen et al., 2023) is an open-source framework developed for efficient wind farm flow and wake interaction modelling. Unlike high-fidelity LES solvers such as AMR-Wind and SOWFA, PyWake employs engineering wake models to predict wind farm performance with reduced computational costs. The framework is designed to facilitate comparisons between different wake models, including analytical wake deficit models (Jensen, 1983; Bastankhah and Porté-Agel, 2014; Blondel and Cathelain, 2020) and models based on eddy viscosity (Ainslie, 1988). These models estimate the velocity deficit and turbulence intensity within turbine wakes, capturing essential flow characteristics with reasonable accuracy for wind farm optimization and control studies.

The tool provides built-in functionalities for computing power production, wake deficits, and turbulence intensity across wind farms, making it particularly useful for layout optimization and energy yield assessments. Furthermore, it supports wake steering strategies by integrating yaw control methodologies, enabling studies on the potential benefits of wake redirection for power maximization.

The modularity of PyWake allows users to select different atmospheric conditions, terrain effects, and turbulence models, enhancing its adaptability to various wind farm configurations. The framework is implemented in Python and supports parallel computations to handle large-scale wind farm scenarios efficiently. By offering a balance between computational efficiency and wake modeling accuracy, PyWake serves as a valuable tool for both research and industry applications in wind energy.

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3 Data-driven framework for tuning wake mixing controllers

Unlike wind farm flow control techniques that adjust a static control setpoint such as static induction control or wake steering, the effectiveness of wake mixing techniques (e.g., periodic dynamic induction control or the helix method) also relies on the frequency of excitation. Initial studies on periodic dynamic induction control indicated an optimal frequency for a Strouhal number of $St = 0.25$ (Munters and Meyers, 2018b). The dimensionless Strouhal number is expressed as $St = f \cdot D / U_\infty$, with excitation frequency f , rotor diameter D and inflow velocity U_∞ . Successive simulation (Frederik et al., 2020a; Muscari et al., 2022) and experimental (Frederik et al., 2020b; Hoek et al., 2024b) studies on wake mixing methods observed slightly different optima in the range of $St = 0.2 - 0.4$. These previous studies indicate that the optimal frequency can depend on multiple aspects, such as the ambient conditions, the considered turbine, and the simulation environment.

In Chapter 4, we aim to develop a wake surrogate model that captures the steady-state wake properties of the helix method. To simplify this approach, we will consider only one frequency for the wake model. This optimal frequency will be determined in the current chapter for ambient conditions prevalent at the HKN wind farm site and for similar turbine spacing using the LES code AMR-Wind. These kinds of simulations require several hundreds of CPUs for multiple days, limiting the number of simulations that can be performed to identify the optimal frequency. To reduce the number of simulations that are required to determine the optimal settings for the helix approach, this chapter presents a data-driven approach to controller tuning using LES. The framework utilises Gaussian processes (GP) to obtain a non-parametric model of the helix method's performance based only on measurements from the LES.

3.1 LES measurement results

LES of the two-turbine array specified in Figure 2.2 were run with AMR-Wind. The hub-height wind speed of the ABL was set to $U_\infty = 8$ m/s with a TI of approximately 4%. A single rectangular refinement box was placed around the two turbines, starting from $2D$ upstream of the first turbine and ending after $5D$ behind the second turbine. After refinement, a mesh with 5 m grid cells was obtained, resulting in 56 cells per rotor diameter. Although this mesh is generally too coarse to fully resolve

the tip vortices shed by the rotor, previous studies on the helix method have shown that the large-scale flow structures are adequately modelled (Taschner et al., 2023). Finally, the simulation was run for a total of 4200 s, of which the first 600 s was used to let the wake develop and only the last 3600 s were considered for analysis. The simulation time step was set to $\Delta t = 0.05$ s.

Simulations of the helix method were achieved using the built-in functionalities of the ROSCO controller. The controller requires the pitch amplitude, frequency, and the operational mode (e.g. helix CW, helix CCW, or pulse) as inputs. The relevant control signals are then sent to the OpenFAST instances that are running within the LES. Figure 3.1 shows two examples of simulations in AMR-Wind that compare no wind farm flow control (baseline) to one implementation of the helix method. Both instantaneous snapshots show a meandering wake, making it difficult to discern the differences between the two cases on these plots alone. However, when we consider the velocity fields averaged over the total simulation length, we notice a smaller velocity deficit behind the first turbine.

Figure 3.1: Side-by-side comparison of a two-turbine array, of which the upstream turbine is operating normally (a,c) or with the helix method (b,d). Instantaneous velocity fields are shown in the top row of the figure (a,b), whereas the bottom row (c,d) shows the time-averaged velocity fields.

The simulation data required for the data-driven modelling framework are extracted as time series from the OpenFAST output files. An example of such a simulation output is given in Figure 3.2, showing the generator power of the upstream

(T1) and downstream (T2) turbines for the baseline and helix method. The time series shows a slight decrease in power for T1, and a significant increase in power for T2 for most of the simulation time. The measurement domain is then divided into multiple periods of 10 minutes, and the power is averaged over time. The time-averaged power data is subsequently used to compute the relative power gain of the helix method over baseline control, which is then sent to the Gaussian process as training data for. The 10-minute average power measurements also show the variability in power over time resulting from the turbulent eddies that hit the turbines. This implies that the power increase achieved by the helix varies over time.

Figure 3.2: Power generated by the upstream (T1) and downstream (T2) turbines over time (left), and the 10-minute average power comparing baseline control to the helix method (right). The vertical dashed lines indicate the 10-minute intervals used for averaging.

3.2 Gaussian process regression

The data-driven tuning framework presented in this deliverable uses Gaussian processes (Rasmussen and Williams, 2006) to model turbine power as a function of pitch frequency and amplitude. We assume that 10-minute average power data-points (\mathbf{y}) belong to a multivariate Gaussian distribution

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y} \\ \mathbf{y}^* \end{bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N} \left(\mathbf{0}, \begin{bmatrix} K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}) + \sigma_n^2 I & K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}^*) \\ K(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{x}) & K(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{x}^*) \end{bmatrix} \right), \quad (3.1)$$

that depends on control input combinations of amplitude and frequency (\mathbf{x}). Furthermore, \mathbf{y}^* refers to the inferred power for possible control inputs \mathbf{x}^* . The covariance matrix (K) is defined using a Matérn covariance function, while σ_n represents noise,

accounting for power variability due to inflow fluctuations. After optimising a set of hyperparameters, we compute the posterior distribution of the model, resulting in a mean and variance for the input locations (\mathbf{x}^*) using the following equations:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}^* = K(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{x}) (K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}) + \sigma_n^2 I)^{-1} \mathbf{y}, \quad (3.2)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}^* = K(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{x}^*) - K(\mathbf{x}^*, \mathbf{x}) (K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}) + \sigma_n^2 I)^{-1} K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}^*). \quad (3.3)$$

For the Gaussian process to effectively identify the contribution of both turbines to the total power, the model is split into two parts with their own set of hyperparameters. Hence, we obtain a Gaussian process model that estimates the power loss of T1 ($\boldsymbol{\mu}_{T1}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{T1}$) due to the helix actuation, and a Gaussian process model that estimates the power gain or loss for turbine T2 ($\boldsymbol{\mu}_{T2}, \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{T2}$) due to the affected wake recovery. A useful property of Gaussian processes is that the sum of two Gaussian processes is also a Gaussian process. Therefore, we can model the mean and variance of the total power gain as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{T1+T2} = \boldsymbol{\mu}_{T1} + \boldsymbol{\mu}_{T2}, \quad (3.4)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{T1+T2}^2 = \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{T1}^2 + \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{T2}^2. \quad (3.5)$$

3.3 Controller tuning results

The GP modelling framework presented in the previous section will now be used to model the power increase of the counterclockwise (CCW) helix implementation. We first demonstrate the GP model for a fixed pitch amplitude of $A_\theta = 2.5^\circ$. The model is initialised using 10-minute average data samples from three separate simulations that employed the helix method at different frequencies. Figure 3.3 shows the three GP models for T1, T2, and the total power gain that were generated from this initial dataset. A clear decrease in power is visible for T1 when the helix is active, becoming more significant for lower pitch frequencies. However, the second turbine sees a large improvement in generated power for increasing Strouhal numbers. The combination of the two GP models indicates that the total power of the array starts improving over baseline operation from $St = 0.1$. The GP model also expects power improvements for $St > 0.2$, although the uncertainty at higher frequencies is very high due to the lack of data samples in that region. It should be noted that for actuation at $St = 0$, the turbine is pitching the blades at the same frequency as the rotor is spinning, meaning that the thrust force vector has a constant direction over time.

Once the GP model has been initialised, we can determine the control settings for the next LES run. After each new simulation, the hyperparameters of the GP model are optimised again. Figure 3.4 presents several iterations of the GP model as additional data samples are added. Initially, the model focuses on exploring the

Figure 3.3: Power ratio of the helix method over baseline operation. From top to bottom, the figure shows the estimated power of turbine T1, turbine T2 and the combined power of the turbine array. Samples from the LES used to train the model are denoted by the \times -marks. The solid black line indicates the estimated power ratio of the different GP models, and the shaded areas show the uncertainty bounds of the estimated mean power.

input space. Once a clear optimal frequency range has been identified for Strouhal numbers between $St = 0.2 - 0.4$, the GP exploits this knowledge to acquire additional measurement samples within this range. After the latest iteration, we notice that the GP estimates show little variation in this frequency range. The power increase for the considered pitch amplitude seems to settle at approximately 4%. The measurement samples also indicate that where the helix method is effective, large variations in the power ratio occur.

The next step in the modelling framework is to expand the GP model to include the pitch amplitude. This requires only a small alteration to the GP model, consisting of adding an extra hyperparameter. The same approach for selecting the control settings for the LES runs is adopted as in the previous example, focusing first on exploration, followed by maximising the power gain. The final version of the GP models are presented in Figure 3.5 as contour maps of the power ratio as a function of frequency and pitch amplitude. From the GP model of turbine T1, we see a clear decrease in power for lower frequencies and increasing pitch amplitudes. For the second turbine, the power ratio keeps rising for increasing pitch amplitudes. When combining the models of both turbines, we obtain a contour map for the total power

Figure 3.4: Power ratio of the helix method over baseline operation for the two-turbine array. Samples from the LES used to train the model are denoted by the \times -marks. The solid black line indicates the estimated power ratio of the different GP models, and the shaded areas show the uncertainty bounds of the estimated mean power. The subplots from (a)-(f) show different iterations of the GP model after additional data has been acquired.

ratio indicating a clear optimum. The optimum indicates that at some point, the power loss of the actuated turbine (T1) can no longer be compensated by the power of the downstream turbine (T2). The optimum power ratio was identified at 7.5% for an amplitude of $A_\theta = 4^\circ$ and a frequency of $St = 0.25$, which is in good agreement with previous studies (Munters and Meyers, 2018b; Frederik et al., 2020a).

Figure 3.5 also shows the two-dimensional estimates of the GP models with uncertainty bounds for the optimal frequency and amplitude. The model for T1 can estimate the power loss with high certainty, with the only uncertainty arising from the lack of samples at higher frequencies. Power losses of up to 5% are visible for increasing amplitudes at the optimal frequency. The models for T2 and the overall power have a similar shape, with higher uncertainty on the estimates. Interestingly, the range of optimal frequencies seems to narrow as the pitch amplitude increases. When operating the helix with pitch amplitudes up to 2.5° this could offer some additional flexibility on the selected frequency. In this case, the optimal frequency is not only determined by maximum power gain, but also by minimum fatigue loading.

Figure 3.5: Power ratio of the helix method over baseline operation. The figure shows the estimated power of turbine T1 (a), turbine T2 (b) and the combined power of the turbine array (c). Samples from the LES used to train the model are denoted by the \times -marks. The contour maps indicate the estimated mean power ratio of the different GP models. The dashed lines denote the optimal frequency and amplitude for the total power gain. The accompanying estimates and uncertainty bounds are shown above and to the right of the contour maps.

Modelling the performance of wake mixing techniques has thus far been limited to the CCW helix method. In Figure 3.6, the model is modified to include clockwise (CW) simulations of the helix method. For this model, we assume the shape of the Gaussian process model for the CW helix is similar to the CCW version. The model is therefore extended by mirroring the frequency axis to negative Strouhal numbers. Note that this refers to the contribution of the Strouhal number to the actual pitching frequency, which is given by

$$f_{\beta} = f_r + f_e = f_r + \frac{St \cdot U_{\infty}}{D}. \quad (3.6)$$

Here, f_{β} refers to the pitching frequency of the blades, f_r the rotational frequency of the turbine, and f_e the frequency of the helix excitation. For the CW excitation of the helix, the blade pitching frequency will be below the rotational frequency of the turbine. Figure 3.6 shows that the CW helix method achieves similar power gains as CCW for pitch amplitudes up to 2° . For higher pitch amplitudes, that gain remains fairly constant, which means that the power loss of the actuated turbine is not overcompensated by the power gain of the downstream turbine.

The tuning framework has so far been demonstrated for a single free-stream wind speed and turbulence level. However, the controller performance for additional simulation conditions could potentially be modelled by adding inputs covering wind speed, turbulence and atmospheric stability, among others. This extension remains for future work. For the remaining contributions of this deliverable, the optimal controller settings that were obtained in this chapter will be used.

Figure 3.6: Power ratio of the helix method over baseline operation. The figure shows the estimated combined power of the turbine array, comparing the CW and CCW helix implementations. Samples from the LES used to train the model are denoted by the \times -marks. The dashed line denotes the optimal amplitude for the total power gain. The accompanying estimates and uncertainty bounds are shown above the contour map.

4 Quasi-steady wake model for wake mixing methods

This chapter focuses on the development and validation of a quasi-steady wake model for assessing wake mixing strategies in wind farms, following the approach described in (Dammann et al., 2025). While high-fidelity LES provide detailed wake dynamics, their computational cost limits their applicability in iterative optimization and control design. In contrast, quasi-steady models offer a more computationally efficient approach by capturing the dominant wake behavior without resolving transient flow features. The model presented here incorporates insights from high-fidelity simulations to improve wake deficit predictions under helix actuation. The developed helix surrogate model is benchmarked against wake steering control under consideration of the reference wind farm defined in Chapter 2, showing how these two control strategies compare and highlighting potential synergies in future control algorithms. By providing a balance between accuracy and efficiency, this work supports the broader objectives of the deliverable, which is enabling the rapid evaluation of flow control techniques and facilitating their integration into wind farm optimization frameworks. The results from this chapter serve as a foundation for subsequent sections on benchmarking control strategies and developing real-time operational tools.

4.1 Steady-state helix surrogate model

The steady-state helix surrogate model used in this study integrates multiple engineering models to enhance wake deficit predictions. Specifically, it incorporates a single wake velocity deficit model, as described by Blondel and Cathelain (2020), which is fine-tuned using high-fidelity data. In addition, it includes a Blockage Deficit model from Branlard and Gaunaa (2015) and a turbine-induced turbulence model following Frandsen (2007).

In the literature, a steady-state helix surrogate model was previously implemented within the FLOW Redirection and Induction in Steady State (FLORIS) framework (NREL, 2024). However, the study at hand introduces a new approach, utilizing the PyWake framework coupled to an alternative velocity deficit model instead. For wake steering operation, the wake deflection and redirection model from Jiménez et al. (2010) is applied. The velocity used for calculating turbine power, wake deficit, and added turbulence is determined using 21 evaluation points across the rotor

plane, following the approach from Abramowitz and Stegun (1970). The single wake model from Blondel and Cathelain (2020) was selected based on its strong agreement with high-fidelity data, as demonstrated in Section 4.3. All engineering models are integrated into the PyWake framework described in Section 2.2.4. Additionally, a dedicated IEA-22MW turbine model was developed within PyWake, incorporating helix-amplitude and turbulence-dependent thrust and power coefficients derived from OpenFAST (National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 2024), a widely used aeroelastic simulation tool for wind turbines. Turbulence generation follows the IEC Kaimal spectrum and is simulated using the TurbSim software (Kelley and Jonkman, 2007).

The steady-state wake model estimates the velocity deficit behind the turbine by expressing it as the product of the maximum velocity deficit $C(\tilde{x})$ and a shape function $f(\tilde{r})$. The parameters \tilde{x} , $\tilde{\sigma}$, and \tilde{r} denote the axial distance from the turbine, the characteristic wake width, and the radial distance from the wake center, respectively, normalised by the turbine diameter d_0 :

$$\frac{U_\infty - U_w}{U_\infty} = C(\tilde{x})f(\tilde{r}) = C(\tilde{x})e^{-\tilde{r}^n/(2\tilde{\sigma}^2)}. \quad (4.1)$$

Here, U_∞ represents the freestream velocity, while U_w is the wake velocity. The maximum velocity deficit $C(x)$ is defined as:

$$C(x) = 2^{2/n-1} - \sqrt{2^{4/n-2} - \frac{nC_T}{16\Gamma(2/n)\sigma^{4/n}}}, \quad (4.2)$$

where n denotes the Super Gaussian Order, and Γ is a parameter that restores the original form of $C(\tilde{x})$ proposed by Bastankah and Porté-Agel (Bastankah and Porté-Agel, 2014) when $\Gamma(1) = 1$ and $n = 2$. The characteristic wake width (σ) is defined as a function of turbulence intensity:

$$\sigma = (a_s T_i + b_s)x + c_s \sqrt{\beta}, \quad (4.3)$$

where β depends on the turbine's thrust coefficient C_T :

$$\beta = \frac{1}{2} \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 - C_T}}{\sqrt{1 - C_T}}. \quad (4.4)$$

Finally, the analytical Super Gaussian parameter n is given by:

$$n = a_f e^{b_f x} + c_f, \quad (4.5)$$

where $(a_s, b_s, c_s, a_f, b_f, c_f)$ are calibration parameters that will be fitted to the LES data in Section 4.3.2.

4.2 High-fidelity simulation setup

All large eddy simulations in this chapter were conducted using the modelling tool AMR-Wind, as mentioned in Section 2.2.2. The setup was designed so that the turbine wake can be examined without external disturbances such as the ground effect, gravitational force, or the turbine tower, which is crucial for its representation through an axisymmetrical velocity deficit model. To isolate the wake influence from boundary layer interactions, all single-turbine simulations were conducted under uniform inflow conditions without shear or veer. The inlet flow consisted of a constant velocity field superimposed with fluctuations derived from a precomputed synthetic turbulence field following the IEC-Kaimal spectrum, generated using the open-source software TurbSim (Kelley and Jonkman, 2007).

The process of generating the uniform homogeneous turbulence field is illustrated in Figure 4.1. The left panel displays the direct output from TurbSim, while the right panel presents the extracted velocity fluctuations at a given vertical position within a two-dimensional turbulence slice. To ensure consistency with the intended inflow conditions, the mean wind speed at each height was computed over the entire simulated time series. The corresponding power law profile was then reconstructed using the same shear exponent α , as in the original field generation, following

$$u = u_{ref} \cdot \left(\frac{z}{z_{ref}} \right)^\alpha, \quad (4.6)$$

with u_{ref} denoting the reference free-stream wind speed and z_{ref} the specified reference height. This reference velocity profile was subtracted from the raw velocity data, yielding the fluctuations shown on the right side of the figure.

Figure 4.1: Illustration of power shear extraction for uniform homogeneous turbulence field generation.

The simulation domain, illustrated in Figure 4.2 extends $20D$ in streamwise direction and $10D$ in both lateral dimensions. The rotor is placed $4D$ from the Inlet, leaving $16D$ for wake examination. The domain was discretised into uniform cells

of $\Delta x \approx 0.035D$ with a single refinement around the turbine rotor amounting to approximately 56 cells per diameter. The refinement starts $2D$ upstream of the rotor and extends $5D$ downstream with respective $4D$ uniform lateral spacings. All simulations were conducted with a time step of $\Delta t = 0.02s$ to satisfy the CFL stability condition.

Figure 4.2: Sketch of the LES domain. The length of the domain is $20D$ in streamwise direction and $10D$ in both lateral directions. The turbine rotor is placed at a distance of $4D$ from the inlet.

4.3 Calibration and validation

To capture the time-averaged flow field of the helix approach, the calibration parameters (b_s , c_s , b_f , c_f) of the surrogate model described in Section 4.1 were tuned using flow field data from a single turbine operating under baseline operation and helix actuation. The calibration parameter a_f was kept at its initial value to maintain the super-Gaussian order, as outlined by Blondel and Cathelain (2020).

4.3.1 Wake model calibration

The following steps outline the procedure used to calibrate the surrogate model with LES data:

1. High-fidelity simulation data were extracted as flow slices containing 560×280 points with a time resolution of 1 s. These slices were time-averaged over 10 helix periods, using $T_{1P} = \frac{1}{f}$, where f represents the helix actuation frequency. The obtained time-averaged slices (xy -plane, xz -plane, and two diagonal cross-stream planes) were then further averaged to represent the axisymmetric flow field.
2. The surrogate model was configured to replicate the axisymmetric flow field using the same domain specifications as the extracted high-fidelity slices. The

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turbine model used in the LES was recreated in the PyWake framework, employing power and thrust coefficient curves derived from OpenFAST simulations.

3. A cost function was established to minimise the absolute error between the AMR-wind flow field data and the predicted PyWake flow field for the parameters $\psi = [b_s, c_s, b_f, c_f]$:

$$\psi_{opt} = \arg \min_{\psi} \sum_{i=1}^N |v_{LES,i} - v_{model,i}|. \quad (4.7)$$

The calibration parameter a_s was held constant at its predefined value of 0.17, which represents the scaling of the characteristic wake width σ with ambient turbulence intensity TI_a . A full determination of a_s would require multiple simulations at varying TI_a values, which will be conducted in future studies. Thus, for the current analysis, the variation of σ with TI_a is assumed to be constant.

4.3.2 Calibration results

The methodology of Section 4.1 was implemented in Python, using a parallelised constrained genetic algorithm (GA) combined with a simulated annealing algorithm for local refinement. The GA was developed using the open source pygad library (Gad, 2023). The optimised parameters ψ_{opt} are presented in Table 4.1. The consistent trends in the calibrated parameters across varying helix amplitudes suggest that the optimization was not overfitted to a single flow field.

Table 4.1: Calibrated parameters with constant $a_s = 0.17$ for different pitch angle amplitudes of the helix approach.

	b_s	c_s	b_f	c_f
Baseline	0.020	0.202	-1.130	2.767
Helix (1°)	0.031	0.191	-2.570	2.983
Helix (3°)	0.047	0.189	-2.518	3.128
Helix (5°)	0.054	0.215	-0.775	2.536

Figure 4.3 illustrates the calibration results, showing that the helix method leads to faster wake recovery and increased wake spreading compared to the baseline case, which is well captured by the tuned surrogate model. However, the time-averaged velocity field exhibits a double Gaussian velocity deficit, especially in the far-wake region, which is not well captured by the surrogate model. This limitation arises because the model was originally developed for baseline operation and does not fully account for the velocity field nuances introduced by helical perturbations.

Figure 4.3: Results of the calibration procedure for baseline operation (left) and helix operation (right). The top row shows an instantaneous snapshot of the xy -plane at $t = 2000$ s, with black lines indicating the lateral width of the turbulent flow. The middle row presents the time-averaged axisymmetric velocity field, while the bottom row shows the calibrated surrogate model.

4.3.3 Validation results

Due to the high computational cost of ALM-LES simulations for entire wind farms, validation was conducted using a single turbine LES simulation under different ambient conditions. Specifically, the model was tested at a higher wind speed of 9 ms^{-1} and an increased ambient turbulence intensity of $TI_a = 5.7\%$.

A visual comparison between the calibrated model and the simulation results is shown in Figure 4.4. In general, the model aligns well with the simulation data, particularly in the mid- and far-wake regions. However, discrepancies are more pronounced in the near-wake region. For the helix calibration, the surrogate model underestimates the velocity deficit in the wake center, likely due to a mismatch in the shaping function used to represent the velocity deficit. Ongoing efforts focus on refining the model, particularly by modifying the shaping function of the velocity deficit. These improvements aim to enhance the model's ability to capture the time-averaged velocity deficit variations induced by helix actuation. By incorporating the effects of control input parameters, such as actuation amplitude, the updated model is expected to provide a more accurate representation of the resulting flow field. For the time being, the model has proven sufficiently accurate in capturing the helix flow field to provide a reasonable estimate of the effects of helix actuation, especially at the wind farm level.

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Figure 4.4: Error analysis of the calibrated model under different ambient conditions. Red regions indicate overestimation of wind speed, while blue regions indicate underestimation.

4.4 HKN case study

The following section presents a case study comparing the newly developed helix wake model to wake steering and baseline control for the reference wind farm defined in Section 2.1. The analysis evaluates the effectiveness of each control strategy concerning the whole wind rose of the reference wind farm.

4.4.1 Baseline operation

Figure 4.5 compares flow fields under baseline operation, wake steering, and helix control for a wind speed of 8 ms^{-1} and an ambient turbulence intensity of $TI_a = 4\%$ at a wind direction of 201° . This wind direction was chosen because it results in the highest wake losses among all studied wind directions. The significant wake overlap observed at this angle greatly affects power output and increases turbine fatigue, making it an essential case for operational optimization and turbine layout design.

Figure 4.5a illustrates the performance of all turbines operating in a conventional greedy mode. As expected, the front-row turbines achieve maximum possible power output under the given ambient conditions. However, downstream turbines experience significant power reductions due to wake interactions, with the most substantial losses reaching up to 69.7% in the lower-left cluster. These results highlight the critical impact of wake interactions on farm-wide energy production. The total power output of the farm under baseline conditions is 63.1 MW.

Figure 4.5: Flow field at hub height (170 m) of all turbines for wind speed 8 ms^{-1} and $TI_a = 4\%$ for baseline operation (a), wake steering operation (b), and helix operation (c) for wind direction 201° .

4.4.2 Wake steering

To simulate wake steering, the baseline surrogate wake model was combined with the wake redirection model from Jiménez et al. (2010). The yaw angles were optimised using a serial refinement approach following Fleming et al. (2022b), considering a set of yaw angles in 1° increments ranging from -20° to 20° . For each wind direction, the yaw angle of each turbine was varied sequentially from upstream to downstream to maximise total farm power output:

$$\gamma_{opt_n} = \arg \max_{\gamma_n} \sum_{i=1}^N P_i. \quad (4.8)$$

As shown in Figure 4.5b, the most upstream turbine in the left-side cluster experiences power losses due to the inclined inflow. However, all downstream turbines benefit from increased power output, resulting in a total farm power increase to 65.2 MW, representing a 3.03% improvement over baseline operation.

4.4.3 Helix actuation

Figure 4.5c presents the wind farm operating under helix actuation. The pitch angles of the surrogate helix amplitude were optimised using an algorithm following the serial refinement approach in Section 4.4.2. The helix amplitudes of the upstream turbines were adjusted along the streamwise direction, and the total farm power output was compared to the baseline.

The results indicate that helix actuation was consistently applied whenever downstream turbines were affected by wake interactions. In all cases, the algorithm selected the highest possible helix amplitude of 5° , likely due to the minimal power losses associated with helix actuation relative to the downstream power gains. How-

ever, it is important to note that this surrogate model prioritises power maximization alone. Since helix actuation increases turbine loading, an optimization approach that accounts for structural loads may select lower amplitudes to balance power gains with mechanical stress.

The total farm power output under helix operation reached 70.3 MW, corresponding to an 11.4% improvement over baseline operation and a 7.82% gain compared to wake steering.

Figure 4.5c shows that the power reduction in the first turbine of the left-side cluster is less pronounced than in Figure 4.5b, while the three following turbines exhibit higher power gains. However, the last turbine in the array produces less power than in the wake steering case.

Another notable effect can be observed in the right-side cluster, where wake steering results in a higher cumulative power output than helix control. Since the upstream turbine experiences a relatively small yaw misalignment, its power reduction is similar in both methods. However, the downstream turbine benefits more from wake steering, leading to higher overall effectiveness in this scenario. This is likely due to the relatively large downstream distance between the turbines, allowing wake deflection to develop more effectively.

Figure 4.6 illustrates the total farm power output estimated by PyWake across different wind directions. The upper plot highlights wind directions with significant wake losses, while the lower plot shows the relative power gains from wake steering and helix control. Initially, both strategies appear to provide comparable improvements over baseline operation. However, a closer examination of normalised power output reveals distinct performance trends.

Helix actuation tends to outperform wake steering when turbines are aligned in high-wake-overlap conditions. Conversely, wake steering is more effective when wind directions are slightly misaligned with turbine arrays, allowing for greater optimisation potential. In terms of maximum gains over baseline operation, wake steering achieves a peak increase of 12.5%, whereas helix actuation reaches a maximum gain of 11.9% according to our model.

Figure 4.6: Total farm power estimated by PyWake per wind direction. The upper plot shows the overall power output of baseline operation, optimised wake steering operation, and optimised helix operation. The bottom plot shows both, wake steering and helical actuation normalised with the baseline case.

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5 Geometric wind farm control optimisation methods

The steady-state models used to simulate different control strategies discussed in the previous sections allow to optimise the control variables of each individual turbine. The model estimations of improved wind farm performance need to be validated in a high-fidelity environment. Moreover, these solutions can then be parameterised using the physical insights gained from these models and the geometric properties of the wind farm. A complete description of this methodology will be included in the deliverables related to WP5 and only a brief overview is included here to motivate its use within WP1. Specifically, this technique is adopted within this work package to determine the yaw angles adopted in the LES simulations described in the next Chapter 6.

5.1 Parameterisation of the optimal control strategy

The parameterisation of the optimal control strategy has been developed by Stanley et al. (2023) and Baricchio et al. (2024), and can be summarised in the following steps:

1. The steady-state wake models developed in this work package are used to calculate the optimal control strategies for a wide range of conditions. These include different wind speeds and directions, but also various farm sizes and layouts. Therefore, a database of optimal control variables is created, registering the values associated to each turbine for any given condition.
2. Based on physical insights and empirical observations, analytical relations are derived to express the values of the optimal control variables (e.g. yaw angles and helix amplitude) as a function of the flow condition (e.g. wind speed, wind direction, turbulence intensity) and the layout geometry, such as the cross-stream and downstream distances between neighbouring turbines.
3. The database is used to tune these relations and to evaluate their effectiveness to approximate the optimal control variables for each turbine.

The method referred to as the “Geometric Yaw: exponential corrected approach” developed by Baricchio et al. (2024) has been applied to approximate the optimal

yaw angles for the case study depicted in Figure 2.2. This technique determines the values of the yaw offsets based on the reciprocal positions of multiple downstream turbines and the effective wind speed during baseline operation. Further details on this method will be provided in the deliverable related to WP5. These geometric yaw angles have been used to test the effectiveness of the control strategy through the LES simulations described in the Chapter 6. Moreover, these values are compared with the optimised yaw angles obtained using the Serial-Refine method (Fleming et al., 2022a), both neglecting and considering uncertainty in the wind direction. In the latter case, the methodology of Rott et al. (2018) is applied, where deviations from the nominal wind direction are tested and the correspondent power values are weighted based on a Gaussian distribution centred on the nominal wind direction value. Specifically, a value of $\sigma = 5^\circ$ has been used. These results are depicted in Figures 5.1 and 5.2, where the yaw angles calculated with the different methods and their respective power gains are shown. These values have been obtained through simulations based on steady-state wake models available in PyWake. This preliminary analysis enables to select appropriate wind directions values to test with the LES solver to prove the benefit of this control strategy.

Figure 5.1: Yaw angles for the wind direction of 206° and the wind speed of 10 m/s obtained with the Geometric Yaw (exponential corrected approach) and the Serial-Refine (referred to as "Optimal yaw") methods. The robust approach considers an uncertainty on the wind direction of $\sigma = 5^\circ$.

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Figure 5.2: Power increase obtained with PyWake when wake steering is applied to the HKN corner for a wind speed of 10 m/s. Different yaw angles are tested, calculated with different methods.

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6 Benchmarking wind farm flow control methods

This chapter presents a benchmark of wind farm flow control (WFFC) techniques acquired from LES. The benchmark is split into three parts, consisting of different subsets of the HKN wind farm as indicated in Figure 2.2. This set of simulations provides important insights into the flow development behind the turbines under different control strategies. Conducting sub-cluster simulations helps save computational time and allows for the identification of optimal conditions for more computationally intensive simulations.

6.1 Case study I: two-turbine array

For the two-turbine array, different types of wind farm flow control for wake mixing will be considered. First, a comparison between static and dynamic yaw control is made using large-eddy simulations from SOWFA. This is followed by a detailed wake steering analysis including multiple yaw misalignments. Finally, a direct comparison is made of static induction control, wake steering, and wake mixing techniques.

6.1.1 Static and dynamic yaw control

As described in Section 2.2.3, SOWFA was used to explore the potential of yaw control techniques. Both static and dynamic control methods are applied first to a single turbine, and then to a subset of two turbines. The first set of simulations aims to understand the behavior of the wake behind the turbine. To achieve this, the turbine is subjected to an open-loop dynamic yaw control, where the yaw angle varied sinusoidally (Munters and Meyers, 2018a), following

$$\gamma(t) = \gamma_0 + \hat{\gamma} \sin(2\pi f_\gamma t),$$

where γ_0 is the initial yaw angle, $\hat{\gamma}$ is the amplitude of the oscillation, and f_γ is the frequency of the periodic yaw control.

To analyse the mechanisms contributing to faster wake recovery, the analysis was conducted with a low turbulence intensity (TI) to minimise the impact of the atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) on the wake. Figure 6.1 shows an instantaneous streamwise velocity field obtained at hub height, with different frequencies, and consequently, different Strouhal numbers: $St = \frac{fD}{U_\infty}$, where D is the rotor diameter and U_∞ the freestream wind velocity being investigated.

Figure 6.1: Snapshots of the instantaneous streamwise velocity at hub height for $\hat{\gamma} = 15[\text{deg}]$ and different Strouhal Number. The instantaneous wake center is indicated by the white dots.

For all cases except the reference one ($St = 0$), a clear meandering of the wake is observed. The amplitude of the meandering increases from $St = 0.1$, reaching its maximum for the two cases at $St = 0.25$ and $St = 0.35$, which exhibit similar lateral motions. As the frequency increases further, the amplitude of the meandering begins to decrease, suggesting that if the wake is excited at too high a frequency, the meandering may not reach its full lateral extent (Mühle et al., 2024). Figure 6.1 suggests that the meandering of the wake, induced by dynamic yaw excitation, is a key factor contributing to the increased wake mixing.

Based on the results from the first set of simulations, a second set was performed with a subset of two turbines. The front turbine was initially actuated with a static yaw misalignment at 20° , followed by five different dynamic yaw cases with Strouhal numbers varying as ($St = 0.1 : 0.05 : 0.3$) and at a yaw amplitude $\hat{\gamma} = 10^\circ$, which were selected based on the initial simulations and were also chosen to avoid exceeding the yaw rate limit. These six different control strategies were tested at various spatial distances from the wind turbines, ranging from 3 to 8 rotor diameters, with the distance increasing by one diameter between each simulation.

Figure 6.2 schematically represents the 36 different simulations in terms of the power produced by the actuated turbine, the downstream turbine, and the entire cluster of two turbines. The first subplot highlights the significant difference in power loss between classic wake steering and dynamic yaw. The misaligned turbine loses up to 10% of its power production, whereas in all dynamic yaw actuation cases, the power loss is limited to 2%. No clear trend can be observed in the power loss of the first turbine with respect to the Strouhal number.

On the other hand, the power output of the downstream turbine varies with the Strouhal number. Increasing the Strouhal number enhances the performance of

Figure 6.2: Extracted power of the upstream/actuated turbine, downstream/sensor turbine for different spatial distances, and combined turbine array for different Static and dynamic yaw control strategies. Everything is normalised with respect to the case with no actuation (dashed black line)

the downstream turbine: the greater meandering motion of the wake, observed in the first set of experiments, significantly increases the energy available for the second turbine to extract from the wind. The performance of wake steering shows a comparable gain to the dynamic yaw case but deteriorates as the spatial distance increases.

All control strategies achieve a power gain compared to the greedy control case. The trend observed in the second turbine's performance is reflected in the total power gain. In almost all cases where open-loop dynamic yaw is applied, the power gains are higher compared to static yaw steering. In particular, the cases with $St = 0.2, 0.25$, and 0.3 outperform static wake steering, especially at larger spatial distances. In these three cases, the power trend increases with distance up to $6D$, where the trend shifts and remains constant at larger spatial distances. The maximum total power increase is observed at $6D$ with $St = 0.3$, where a total gain of 13% is achieved.

6.1.2 Detailed study on wake steering

The previous section compared dynamic yaw control to a single case of static yaw control or wake steering. We will now consider the effect of wake steering on total power generation for a larger selection of yaw misalignment angles. The large eddy simulations were performed with AMR-Wind for the same setup as defined in Figure 3 with a similar ABL as in Figure 2.4 for hub height wind speed of $U_\infty = 8$ m/s. The simulations considered the following set of yaw misalignments, $\gamma = [-30^\circ \ 10^\circ \ 20^\circ \ 30^\circ]$, for the upstream turbine. The yaw misalignment is defined such that a positive value indicates a counter-clockwise movement of the turbine with respect to the incoming wind direction. The second turbine, which was placed $5D$ apart, operated without a yaw misalignment.

The average generator power that was extracted by the two turbines is presented in Figure 6.3. As expected, the upstream turbine shows higher power losses as the yaw misalignment increases, and vice versa for turbine T2. The right-hand side of the figure shows the modelled power loss of T1 using the \cos^p law (Bossanyi, 2019), which computes the power of the yawed turbine as

$$P_{Yaw}(\gamma) = P_{BL} \cos^p(\gamma). \quad (6.1)$$

Fitting the simulation data to this power law, resulted in a loss-coefficient value of $p = 2.2$, which can be used to compute the effect of wake steering on power with engineering wake models such as PyWake. Liew et al. (2020) showed that this relation only holds for turbines operating in free-stream, and that the loss-coefficient will increase for turbines operating in wake. The total power of the array shows a minimal improvement for a misalignment of 10° . For higher misalignment values, significant gains are achieved with a maximum 14.9% increase for a yaw misalignment of 30° , which is generally considered as the maximum allowable yaw misalignment.

When comparing the effect of positive and negative yaw misalignments, we see a large difference in overall power gain. As seen in previous studies on wake steering (Fleming et al., 2018; Archer and Vassel-Be-Hagh, 2019), positive yaw angles lead to higher power gains than negative yaw angles. Fleming et al. (2018) show that this is due to the interaction of the counter-rotating vortex pair, which forms due to the misalignment, with the natural rotation of the wake. Additionally, Archer and Vassel-Be-Hagh (2019) claim that positive yaw misalignments enhance the naturally occurring wake deflection, which is the result of the Coriolis effect. The velocity fields given in Figure 6.4 confirm these findings. In the baseline case, we see a small deflection of the wake that is in line with the wind veer profile of Figure 2.4. This deflection is enhanced, and the wake is seen to move upwards for positive yaw misalignments. For the negative yaw misalignment, a smaller deflection sideways and towards the ground is observed.

Figure 6.3: Individual and combined power of the two turbines, normalised by the total power of the baseline scenario, for different yaw misalignment angles. The right hand figure shows the power loss relation of the yawed turbine.

Figure 6.4: Cross-stream slices of the streamwise velocity component at a distance of $4D$ downstream for different yaw misalignments.

The PyWake implementation used in Chapter 5 to optimise the yaw angles for the HKN SW corner does not consider these differences in the yaw misalignment direction. Positive and negative yaw angles will thus predict similar power gains for arrays that are aligned with the incoming wind direction. More advanced wake models such as the one proposed by Martínez-Tossas et al. (2019) are required to give a better estimate of wake steering performance, especially for larger arrays.

6.1.3 Benchmark of wind farm flow control methods in aligned conditions

The two-turbine array from the previous sections is now simulated using different wind farm flow control methods in the ABL from Figure 2.4. The following methods were considered in the simulations:

1. Baseline; normal (greedy) operation for both turbines.
2. Helix; the CCW helix method is used for T1 with an amplitude of $A_\theta = 4^\circ$ and $St = 0.25$.

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3. Pulse; periodic dynamic induction control is used for T1 with an amplitude of $A_\theta = 4^\circ$ and $St = 0.25$.
4. Static induction control (SIC); turbine T1 is derated using a pitch angle offset of $\theta = 2^\circ$.
5. Wake steering; positive yaw misalignment of T1 with an angle of $\gamma = 20^\circ$.
6. Wake steering; negative yaw misalignment of T1 with an angle of $\gamma = -20^\circ$.

The average power measurements of the turbines are shown in Figure 6.5. The wake mixing techniques result in similar power losses for the actuated turbine, but the helix method achieves a higher power gain for the second turbine than the pulse method. With SIC, we see a small decrease in power at T1 due to the suboptimal pitch angle. While the power of T2 improves due to this control strategy, it cannot compensate for the power loss, leading to a small decrease in overall power. This result aligns with previous LES studies on static induction control (Annoni et al., 2016). However, SIC can still be considered for its beneficial effects on fatigue loads, as also seen by Debusscher et al. (2022). The positive and negative yaw misalignment angles for wake steering lead to a similar performance drop for T1. While the power of T2 improves for both scenarios, the positive yaw misalignment angle is more beneficial, as was discussed in the previous section. Overall, the helix method achieved the highest power gain, closely followed by the pulse and wake steering.

Figure 6.5: Power generated by two turbines positioned $5D$ apart for different WFFC methods.

The cross-stream velocity fields for all considered control methods are presented in Figure 6.6. Compared to the wake of the baseline case, the helix method results in a similarly shaped wake with a lower velocity deficit. With the pulse method, the shape of the wake also seems to have been affected, with less skew visible than in

the baseline case. Static induction control results in a slight velocity deficit reduction, without any meaningful shape changes. Finally, the wake steering simulations show the typical kidney-shaped velocity fields, with the positive yaw misalignment having the more pronounced impact on the wake.

Figure 6.6: Cross-stream flow slices $5D$ downstream of the actuated turbines for the following WFFC methods: (a) baseline, (b) Helix method, (c) Pulse method, (d) Static induction control, (e) Wake steering with positive misalignment and (f) wake steering with negative misalignment.

Several studies comparing wake mixing techniques have shown that the helix method outperforms the pulse method (Frederik et al., 2020a; Muscari et al., 2022; Hoek et al., 2024a). However, a more recent study indicated that depending on the ambient conditions, other methods may be more effective (Frederik et al., 2024). For example, in conditions with high wind veer, the *pulse* method achieved better results than the helix method. The results obtained in this deliverable indicate the performance of these methods in the presence of a conventionally neutral boundary layer, with moderate veer and low turbulence intensity. In different conditions, flow control methods other than the helix might offer better performance.

6.2 Case study II: three-turbine array

In this section, we consider the case of a three-turbine array with $4.5D$ spacing as found within the HKN wind farm of Figure 2.2. Large-eddy simulations with the ABL from Figure 2.4 were run for three different control strategies, and two wind

directions. An overview of the simulations is given in Table 6.1. The two wind directions that were considered represent the cases where the three turbines are fully aligned ($\phi = 201^\circ$) and misaligned by 5° ($\phi = 206^\circ$). The simulations compare the performance of the helix method and wake steering with conventional greedy operation. For the helix method, only the first turbine is actuated with the optimal pitch amplitude. The yaw misalignments for the wake steering cases were obtained from the geometric yaw optimization presented in Chapter 5. The most downstream turbine was not misaligned with respect to the main wind direction.

Table 6.1: Overview of the large-eddy simulations that were run for the three-turbine array.

Control method	Wind dir. [$^\circ$]	Pitch amp. [$^\circ$]	Yaw mis. γ_1 [$^\circ$]	Yaw mis. γ_2 [$^\circ$]	Power gain [%]
Baseline	201	n.a.	0	0	n.a.
Helix	201	4.0	0	0	+8.3%
Wake steering	201	n.a.	16	18	+6.9%
Baseline	206	n.a.	0	0	n.a.
Helix	206	4.0	0	0	+1.9%
Wake steering	206	n.a.	14	16	+18.2%

Figure 6.7 shows the average streamwise velocity field at hub-height for the fully aligned case. As expected, the helix method achieves a lower velocity deficit in the wake of the first turbine. Furthermore, the effect of the helix method extends to the wake of the second turbine, which also shows a smaller wake than the baseline case. With wake steering, the misalignment of the first two turbines results in a small deflection of the overall wake that hits the third turbine. When considering the misaligned case of Figure 6.8, we see similar velocity fields for the helix method after the first turbine. However, this effect does not propagate to the wake of the second turbine. For the misaligned case, we see that wake steering is capable of redirecting the wake almost fully from the downstream turbines.

Figure 6.7: Average hub-height velocity fields of a three-turbine array with $4.5D$ spacing and inflow direction $\phi = 201^\circ$. The subplots refer to baseline control (a), the helix method (b) and wake steering (c).

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Figure 6.8: Average hub-height velocity fields of a three-turbine array with $4.5D$ spacing and inflow direction $\phi = 206^\circ$. The subplots refer to baseline control (a), the helix method (b) and wake steering (c).

The results of the three turbine simulations are summarised in Figure 6.9, which shows the average power of the three turbines. When the turbine array is fully aligned with the wind direction, the helix method shows a power gain for both T2 and T3, resulting in an overall power increase of 8.3%. Wake steering shows the highest power gain for turbine T3, as T2 also suffers from some loss in power due to its misalignment. Overall, we still observe a gain of 6.9%. When the array is misaligned by 5° , the roles of the WFFC methods are reversed. The helix method still improves the power of T2, but not that of T3. A total power gain of 1.9% is the result. On the other hand, wake steering is very effective in the misaligned case, achieving an overall power benefit of 18.2%.

The simulation results with the helix method presented in this section only considered the case where the most upstream turbine was actuated. While the helix can be extended to multiple turbines, this is not trivial. Korb et al. (2023) showed that the phase offset in the periodic excitation of two turbines affects the performance. Vondelen et al. (2024) proposed a phase synchronization controller to match the phase of the first helix wake to amplify the helix excitation behind the first turbine. In the context of the helix wake surrogate model and the implementation of the helix method on large turbine arrays, the interaction between multiple turbines requires further study.

Figure 6.9: Average power of a three-turbine array with $4.5D$ spacing for different control methods in case of full alignment with the main wind direction (left) and a misalignment of 5° (right).

6.3 Case study III: HKN SW farm

6.3.1 Simulation Setup

High-fidelity simulations of a 10-turbine subset of the Hollandse Kust Noord (HKN) wind farm (as described in Section 2.1) are conducted in order to benchmark the influence of applying static yaw control to this wind farm. These simulations are performed in LES using Ellipsys3D with the Dynamiks-Hawc2 coupling framework (see Section 2.2.1). In total, 9 simulations of the 10-turbine subset are performed, using 3 different wind directions, the 2 different boundary layer heights, including both baseline and controlled scenarios. Each simulation, including inflow description, wind direction and all turbine yaw angles ($\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_{10}$), are listed below in Table 6.2. For the simulations including static yaw control, the optimised yaw angles are obtained from applying the Geometric Yaw (named YawGeo) or Robust (named YawRob) methods to optimisations maximising wind farm power output, as described in Section 5.

Table 6.2: HKN wind farm simulation cases. Note that positive turbine yaw indicates the turbine yawing clockwise as seen from above. Turbine numbering convention based on Figure 2.2.

Case	h_{BL} [m]	Dir [°]	γ_1 [°]	γ_2 [°]	γ_3 [°]	γ_4 [°]	γ_5 [°]	γ_6 [°]	γ_7 [°]	γ_8 [°]	γ_9 [°]	γ_{10} [°]
Baseline197	500	197	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
YawGeo197	500	197	0	16	16	0	0	16	14	0	5	0
Baseline201	500	201	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
YawGeo201	500	201	0	-18	-18	0	0	-18	-15	0	-4	0
Baseline206	500	206	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
YawGeo206	500	206	0	-16	-16	0	0	-16	-14	0	5	0
YawRob206	500	206	0	-1	-3	0	0	-3	-4	0	3	0
Baseline206 150	150	206	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
YawGeo206 150	150	206	0	-16	-16	0	0	-16	-14	0	5	0

This suite of simulations allows many different comparisons and verifications to take place. Firstly, the power gains from LES for each controlled case can be compared to the PyWake power gain predictions (see Figure 5.2), allowing the engineering wake models to be verified, and each optimisation method to be evaluated. Secondly, by comparing the LES baseline and controlled scenarios across the two boundary layer heights, the influence of the very low boundary layer on the wind farm power and the effectiveness of static yaw control can be investigated. Engineering models such as PyWake cannot represent the low boundary layer height in their inflow parameters (as they are generally only based on mean hub height velocity and turbulence intensity); therefore, comparing the PyWake and LES power gain predictions for the low boundary layer height will show how this limited inflow characterisation can impact the validity of optimal yaw predictions for such flow cases.

All simulations are performed using a computational domain of size $10240 \times 10240 \times 3000$ m. The refined region has size $7952 \times 5964 \times 1136$ m, starting from the inlet in the streamwise direction and the ground plane in the vertical direction, and centred in the lateral direction. The size is sufficient to ensure that no turbine is closer than $1.5D$ from the edge of the refined region, and that all of the boundary layer is included. Inside the refined region, the grid resolution is 16 cells per radius, sufficient to provide convergence of the thrust coefficient to less than 1% and accurately represent the wake behaviour (Hodgson et al., 2021; Hodgson et al., 2023). Outside, the cell size is stretched to the domain boundaries. Similar to deliverable D1.1, different wind directions are obtained by rotating the wind farm coordinates. All simulations are run for a total flow time of 4500 s, in which the first 900 s is used as spinup time where the flow and wakes develop, and data is extracted over the final 3600 s.

6.3.2 Results

Figures 6.10, 6.11, 6.12 and 6.13 show the mean streamwise velocity magnitude on a horizontal plane at hub height for each case, with each figure displaying the baseline and controlled scenarios for an individual flow case (wind direction and/or boundary layer height). The three different wind directions chosen (197° , 201° and 206°) lead to a row of turbines with a spacing of $\approx 4.5D$ (numbered in order T7, T6, T3, T2, T1) being partially aligned one way (197°), almost fully aligned (201°) and partially aligned the opposite way (206°). Therefore, the turbines to which static yaw control is applied based on the input from the yaw optimisation are T7, T6, T3, T2, the first four turbines of this aligned or partially aligned row. In all cases T9 is also slightly yawed, due to the wake somewhat impinging on T4 and/or T5.

For all simulations, strong mean wake deficits are clearly visible, which last significant distances downstream of each turbine. This is due to the very low turbulence intensity of the two inflow cases (3% for the 500 m boundary layer height, and 2.2.%

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Figure 6.10: Mean streamwise velocity on horizontal plane at hub height for wind direction of 197° , with boundary layer height 500 m. Left: Baseline scenario Baseline197; Right: Controlled scenario YawGeo197.

Figure 6.11: Mean streamwise velocity on horizontal plane at hub height for wind direction of 201° , with boundary layer height 500 m. Top left: Baseline scenario Baseline201; Top middle: Controlled scenario YawGeo201.

for the 150 m boundary layer height) leading to slow wake recovery behind the turbines. This therefore makes wake steering through static yaw control more likely to lead to power gains, as not only is there a closely spaced and almost aligned turbine row, but also the baseline case will experience significant wake losses.

As also shown in D1.1, there are substantial differences between the wind farm flows for the two boundary layer heights. The very low boundary layer height of 150 m results in strong changes in velocity magnitude, shear and veer over the rotor area, which affects the wake behaviour. Comparing Figures 6.12 and 6.13 shows that the interaction between the turbines and the top of the boundary layer leads to much wider wakes for the 150 m boundary layer, leading to the top row of turbines appearing more aligned and hence experiencing increased wake effects. However, the engineering wake models used in the yaw optimisation in Chapter 5 cannot take these effects into account, and so the optimised yaw angles are identical between the equivalent 150 m and 500 m boundary layer cases.

The wind farm power outputs are now assessed, to investigate the impact of

Figure 6.12: Mean streamwise velocity on horizontal plane at hub height for wind direction of 206° , with boundary layer height 500 m. Top Left: Baseline scenario Baseline206; Top Right: Controlled scenario YawGeo206; Bottom: Controlled scenario YawRob206.

Figure 6.13: Mean streamwise velocity on horizontal plane at hub height for wind direction of 206° , with boundary layer height 150 m. Left: Baseline scenario Baseline206 150; Right: Controlled scenario YawGeo206 150.

the applied static yaw control on the farm efficiency. Figure 6.14 shows the mean and standard deviation of the total power output of each wind farm, grouped by flow case; Figure 6.15 shows the mean percentage change in power output for each controlled scenario, when compared to the matching baseline scenario.

Figure 6.14 shows that the baseline power output of the wind farm (the blue bars) varies significantly across the three wind directions, and the two boundary layer heights. The 201° case has the aligned row of five turbines, and therefore

Figure 6.14: Mean and standard deviation of total wind farm power output over 1 hr with 1s sampling, for the HKN 10-turbine section, for each flow case.

Figure 6.15: Percentage change in mean total wind farm power output over 1 hr, for each controlled scenario relative to the equivalent baseline scenario.

experiences a lower total power output than the two partially aligned cases, due to the increased wake effects. However, the lowest total power output across the four baseline cases is the 206° case with the 150m boundary layer height. This demonstrates the importance of the inflow characteristics in addition to hub height wind direction and layout in determining wind farm performance, as the interaction

with the boundary layer (visible in Figure 6.13) and the lower turbulence intensity significantly affect the wake behaviour, and hence the wind farm efficiency.

An additional important conclusion from comparing the baseline cases relates to the inflow wind direction. Measuring the wind direction at the inflow to a real wind farm is non-trivial, and often includes significant uncertainties. Even a moderate degree of uncertainty in wind direction could potentially be problematic for this scenario, as within this 9° window of wind direction (197° to 206°), the optimal yaw angles for the aligned row of turbines changes from -16° to $+16^\circ$, and applying the incorrect yaw direction due to imprecise inflow measurement would likely result in a total power loss. The robust optimisation approach attempts to mitigate this risk by assuming an uncertainty of 5° and consequently results in much smaller yaw angles being selected (-1° to -4° rather than -14° to -16°) and hence a smaller power production increase.

Considering Figure 6.15, despite the difference in fidelity of the models, there are some similarities between the percentage power gain predicted by the LES simulations and the predictions from PyWake in Chapter 5 (Figure 5.2) for the 500 m boundary layer cases. The most consequential difference between the predictions of the two models is that for the nearly fully aligned row (201°), the geometric yaw approach results in a power loss in LES, whereas PyWake predicts a power gain of 4%. A low-fidelity model providing a false positive could be a significant issue for industry adoption of wind farm flow control strategies, where avoidance of power losses is a key objective. However, for the partial wake cases (197° and 201°), LES does predict a power gain similar to that from PyWake. For 197° case the LES mean power prediction is higher than the PyWake prediction by around $\approx 1\%$ pt, while for the 206° it is lower by $\approx 2\%$ pt for both the geometric yaw and robust approaches. This asymmetry in the power gain is likely due to a slight asymmetry in the amount of geometric misalignment of the turbine row for the two wind directions. The 197° wind direction leads to a greater turbine misalignment, and hence the wake steering is more effective at increasing the downstream power output.

Both of the geometric yaw 206° LES cases at 500 m and 150 m boundary layer height predict a total power gain due to the applied yaw control, however the percentage increase is much lower for the lower boundary layer height ($\approx 2.5\%$ compared to 7.5%). While in the partial wake 500 m boundary layer cases the LES agrees well with the PyWake predictions, this is not the case for the 150 m boundary layer. The extremely low boundary layer height combined with the large turbine creates an inflow scenario which is unable to be captured by the engineering models used in the yaw optimisation, and hence there is no differentiation between the inflows of the two cases in PyWake, but the difference in the inflow significantly influences the wake behaviour and hence the wind farm efficiency.

Lastly, Figure 6.16 shows the percentage power difference by turbine number in

the farm, to demonstrate where the changes in total wind farm power originate in each case. It is clear that within the range of wind directions considered, the wind farm acts for the most part as an aligned row of five turbines, plus five other turbines that operate almost independently. T4 experiences a slight power increase for wind directions 197° and 201° , and T5 experiences similar for 206° (500 m BL), due to the yaw angle applied to T9, however besides that there is very little interaction between turbines, demonstrated by no yaw control being applied and no changes in power output being observed.

Figure 6.16: Percentage change in mean power output for each turbine, for each controlled scenario related to the equivalent baseline scenario.

In the cases that successfully increase the wind farm power output, this is achieved by yawing the first four turbines in the top row. The first, T7, loses power due to the yaw angle, but even though the subsequent 3 are also yawed, they have a net power gain due to the wake steering applied to those in front. The largest power gains are observed for T1, which is the last turbine in the row of five. The 201° case loses power because the applied yaw results in a net power loss not just at the first turbine, but also all others in the row except the last. This is likely due to the mismatch between a slight misalignment of the row, and the sign of the yaw angle that was applied.

7 Quasi-steady integrated wind farm control on scaled turbines in an experimental wind tunnel

In this chapter, some of the results from the two-turbine simulation setup on dynamic yaw control (DYC) are replicated using scaled wind turbine models. This was done to validate the simulation setup and ensure the findings are genuine and not merely a product of numerical artifacts.

7.1 Wind tunnel setup

A cluster of two scaled wind turbines (Figure 7.1) was installed in the test section of the wind tunnel of the Politecnico di Milano (Bottasso et al., 2014). In this campaign, the G2 wind turbine model developed by TUM was utilized. The turbine has a rotor diameter of $D = 2.0$ m, a hub height of $H_{height} = 1.7$ m, and a tilt angle of $\theta = 6.0$ deg. These turbine models are designed to accurately replicate the wake characteristics of full-scale machines. They incorporate individual pitch control, yaw, and torque regulation, allowing for the implementation of various turbine and farm wake control strategies (Wang et al., 2019).

For the experiments, spires and roughness elements were used to generate the turbulence (Giappino et al., 2005). Different turbulence intensities can be triggered with spires of different numbers, positions, and shapes. A typical offshore boundary layer was replicated experimentally in the wind tunnel. Figure 7.2 shows the wind speed and turbulence intensity profiles that were used during the campaign. The wind speed at hub height was about $U = 5.5$ m/s, and the turbulence intensity at the same height was about $TI = 4\%$. The power-law profile that best fits the velocity distribution in the wind tunnel is given by:

$$U(z) = U_h \left(\frac{z}{z_h} \right)^\alpha,$$

where $\alpha = 0.115$.

The front turbine was subjected to a sinusoidal yaw control in the form of:

$$\gamma(t) = \gamma_0 + \hat{\gamma} \sin(2\pi f_\gamma t),$$

Figure 7.1: Wind Tunnel Experimental Setup.

where γ_0 is the initial yaw angle, $\hat{\gamma}$ is the amplitude of the oscillation, and f_γ is the frequency of the periodic yaw control. The second turbine, positioned $4D$ behind the first, was operated as a sensor to calculate the total power of the cluster. Strain gauges were installed on both turbines at the hub and blade roots, enabling the evaluation of loads.

7.2 Results

The measurement campaign was divided into three different stages. In the first stage (Figure 7.3), the amplitude is kept constant at a value of $\hat{\gamma} = 10\text{deg}$, and the excitation frequency (f_γ) was varied between 0.1 and 1.24 Hz. This allowed for the identification of the optimal frequency, which provides the best power performance at the cluster level. To facilitate the comparison between the dynamic yaw control excitation methodology with other dynamic control strategies and a full-scale turbine, the frequency can also be expressed in terms of Strouhal number: $St = \frac{fD}{U_\infty}$, where D is the rotor diameter and U_∞ the freestream wind velocity. The experimental results show a steep gradient at lower frequencies (small Strouhal numbers) and a plateau beyond a Strouhal number of 0.3. The experimental optimal Strouhal num-

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Figure 7.2: Profile of the wind speed (best power-law profile fit in red) on the left, and turbulence intensity (mean TI in red) inside the wind tunnel

ber observed in this set of experiments is approximately 0.35 (for the downstream turbine). In the previous chapter, open-loop dynamic yaw control was investigated numerically, and an optimal Strouhal number of 0.35 was also identified.

In Figure 7.4, as the amplitude of dynamic yaw increases, the power at the cluster level also increases. A maximum power gain of 10% is observed at an oscillation amplitude of 10° . This phenomenon can be attributed to the enhanced meandering motion of the wake, as discussed in the previous simulation chapter.

The first two sets of experiments enable the identification of the optimal point for overall cluster performance. In the final stage, this optimal point (best oscillation frequency and amplitude) is used to investigate the potential gains achieved by combining dynamic yaw with a static steering technique. Figure 7.5 presents a comparison between conventional wake steering (-20°) and the combined dynamic yaw plus static steering approach.

The peak performance of the cluster was observed at a Strouhal number of approximately 0.4. Additionally, an increase in the values of $\hat{\gamma}$ corresponds to an enhancement in the farm's performance, justified by an increased wake recovery. To ensure realistic and applicable results for real-world turbine applications, a yaw amplitude of 8 degrees was selected for the comparisons between the steering technique and the combined steering plus mixing technique. The results in Figure 7.5 highlight an overall performance gain at the cluster level for all the control strategy: approximately 2% for simple steering, 7.2% for dynamic yaw, and 4.5% for the combined steering and dynamic yaw technique. These results indicate a potential for increasing the farm's performance, with dynamic yaw demonstrating the best overall improvement for the specific experimental conditions.

Figure 7.3: Extracted power of the upstream/actuated turbine, downstream/sensor turbine, and combined turbine array for changing Strouhal number $St = (0.04-0.52)$ normalized to the respective baseline case without any actuation (dashed red line).

Figure 7.4: Extracted power of the upstream/actuated turbine, downstream/sensor turbine, and combined turbine array for changing yaw amplitudes $\hat{\gamma} = (2-10^\circ)$ normalized to the respective baseline case without any actuation (dashed red line).

Figure 7.5: Extracted power of the upstream/actuated turbine, downstream/sensor turbine, and combined turbine array for stating yaw steering (blue bar), dynamic yaw (orange bar), and combined mixing and steering (yellow bar) normalized to the respective baseline case without any actuation (dashed red line).

8 Conclusions

This report presented the results of SUDOCO Task 1.2 on integrated quasi-steady wind farm flow control (WFFC) methods in the form of the contributions listed in Chapter 1. A number of high-fidelity simulations were run to explore the quasi-steady nature of wake control techniques based on reference scenarios and turbine models described in D1.1, and subsequently integrate them into existing engineering wake models.

Chapter 3 presented a data-driven approach for tuning the optimal wake mixing settings employing Gaussian process regression. Data from several large eddy simulations (LES) was collected and given as input to Gaussian processes to model the relative power of the helix method compared to baseline control. Three Gaussian process models were subsequently obtained, one for the turbine applying the helix method, one for the turbine operating in the wake of the upstream turbine, and lastly, a model representing the total relative power of the two turbines. After every completed LES run, the models were updated, and the next set of controller settings were selected based on the expected optimum. After multiple simulations, the optimal settings were identified for a Strouhal number of $St = 0.25$ and a pitch amplitude of $A_\theta = 4^\circ$, achieving a total power gain of approximately 7.5%.

In Chapter 4, the optimal wake mixing settings were used to create a surrogate wake model for wake mixing strategies. Large eddy simulations of an isolated wind turbine were run for different amplitudes of the helix methods. By assuming axisymmetry of the wake, the flow fields from the LES were mapped to a single plane, which was subsequently used to tune the wake model parameters of an existing wake model for different pitch amplitudes. The wake was integrated in the wind farm wake model PyWake. A case study on a 10-turbine cluster of the Hollandse Kust Noord (HKN) wind farm was made by comparing the power gain with the helix method to wake steering. The wake model estimated significant power gains with both the helix method and wake steering with maxima of 11.9% and 12.5%, respectively. When evaluating the model for multiple wind directions, it estimated that helix control can potentially outperform wake steering in scenarios where complete turbine wake overlaps occur within an array. In contrast, wake steering proves more effective in cases of partial wake overlap and increased downstream distances.

Chapter 5 briefly introduced a wind farm control optimisation method that uses the optimal wind farm control settings from the engineering wake models to parameterise the solution space. This allows for a rapid estimation of the optimal control settings, making it very useful for co-design applications that require a large number

of model evaluations. A more detailed description of the method will be provided in D5.1. In the current deliverable, the method was demonstrated for estimating the optimal yaw angles for the 10-turbine HKN cluster. These yaw angles were subsequently used in the LES involving wake steering in Chapter 6.

A benchmark of all WFFC methods obtained from LES of the reference wind farms was presented in Chapter 6. The evaluated methods included *static induction control*, *wake steering*, *the helix method*, *periodic dynamic induction control*, and *dynamic yaw control*. Due to high computational demands, WFFC methods such as the helix method, which required the use of the Actuator Line Method to model the forces of the wind turbine blades acting on the flow, were only simulated for two- and three-turbine arrays.

First, we presented the results of a study comparing dynamic and static yaw control for a two-turbine array. Different yaw frequencies were evaluated, with $St = 0.3$ resulting in the highest total power gain of 13%. Compared to static yaw control (wake steering) with a yaw misalignment of 20° , dynamic yaw control showed much better performance. Next, a more detailed look into wake steering was given by applying different yaw misalignment angles to the upstream turbine. From the simulation results, we were able to determine the power loss coefficient for yawing the IEA-22MW turbine. Furthermore, we showed that positive yaw misalignments can achieve higher power gains than negative angles in the case that turbines are fully aligned with the incoming wind direction. Finally, simulations of the two-turbine array were directly compared all the different WFFC methods. For this particular setup, the helix method was able to achieve the highest increase in total power.

The simulations were extended to a three-turbine array with $4.5D$ spacing, similar to some scenarios found in the HKN wind farm. For these simulations, we only compared the helix method with wake steering. For the latter, we applied the yaw misalignments estimated with the geometric yaw optimisation method discussed in Chapter 5. When the turbines were fully aligned, the helix method slightly outperformed wake steering. However, when we changed the wind direction by 5° , a large improvement for wake steering over the helix method was observed.

Chapter 6 was concluded with a wake steering case study of the 10-turbine HKN subset. Several cases with large amounts of wake interaction were considered, comparing full and partial alignment of wind turbine arrays. Furthermore, the wind farm was simulated for two atmospheric boundary layers with inversion heights of 150 m and 500 m. In the case that several turbines were fully aligned, the applied yaw misalignments were not able to achieve an overall power gain. However, for the two wind directions that result in partial wake overlap, wake steering was able to achieve power gains above 10%. Interestingly, the boundary layer height had a significant impact on the performance of wake steering. For the 150 m boundary layer, the absolute power production decreased with respect to the 500 m bound-

ary layer. Furthermore, the performance boost from wake steering dropped from approximately 8% to less than 3%.

Chapter 7 presented the results of a wind tunnel experiment on dynamic yaw control. For the same two-turbine setup used in Chapter 6, dynamic yaw control showed similar levels of power improvements as seen in the LES. Additionally, the combined application of static and dynamic yaw control was investigated. Although the downstream turbine saw an increase in power production with the combined control strategy, it was not able to exceed the overall power gain of dynamic yaw control.

This deliverable provided fundamental information on existing and novel wind farm flow control techniques. Using the data-driven controller tuning framework, wake mixing controller settings can be identified with a limited number of LES. Furthermore, an engineering wake model for wake mixing strategies was developed and integrated into PyWake. This model will be integrated into WP2 on load surrogate models, WP4 on the control room of the future, and WP5 on co-design. The LES that were run to benchmark WFFC techniques, will be used in later work packages for validation. Finally, the WFFC methods that were covered in this deliverable will be further explored in T1.3 on time-varying wind farm control.

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